

Determination of the Lens Mass and Distance of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705

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Abstract

I report on OGLE-2018-BLG-0705, an event simultaneously observed by ground-based telescopes/observatories and the Spitzer Space Telescope. The ground-based data exhibit finite source effects, yielding the microlensing parameter ρ and, in turn, a measurement of the Einstein ring radius, θ_E . Combining the ground-based and space-based observations yields the microlensing parallax, π_E , which, when combined with θ_E , allows for the determination of the lens mass and the distance to the lens, up to a two-fold degeneracy in magnitude of π_E . However, since OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 is a high-magnification event, this degeneracy does not prevent the determination of M_L and D_L . OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 is a single-lens system, where the lens has mass $M_L = 0.74 \pm 0.05 M_\odot$ and the distance to the lens is $D_L = 2.2 \pm 0.1$ kpc. There have been only about ten other single-lens systems where M_L and D_L could be determined from finite source effects and parallax. Analysis of stellar proper motions indicates that the lens star appears likely to be in the star cluster NGC 6544 and breaks the direction degeneracy in π_E . Moreover, the measurement of $D_L = 2.2 \pm 0.1$ kpc perhaps indicates that the previously reported distance to NGC 6544 of $D_{cluster} = 2.6 \pm 0.27$ kpc is too large.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 A Brief History of Microlensing

When Einstein first formulated his theory of general relativity between 1907 and 1915, one of the primary conflicts between his predictions and those of Newtonian mechanics was the difference in how strongly gravity would bend light's path. Newton's particulate understanding of interactions between gravity and light predicted that a gravitational field would act directly on the particles of light that passed through it, accelerating them towards the center of mass. Einstein's relativistic understanding of these interactions predicted that gravity would warp spacetime, which is the very fabric of the universe. Since light travels through spacetime, this curvature in spacetime would lead light's path, as perceived by an observer, to have been bent at an angle twice as large as that which Newton's theory predicted (Einstein, 1936).

In 1917, Sir Frank Watson Dyson proposed using an upcoming total solar eclipse to measure the deflection of light by a gravitational field. He realized that the eclipse on May 29, 1919 would occur when the Hyades star cluster was passing behind the Sun. Therefore, the light from the cluster would have to pass through the Sun's gravitational field before reaching Earth, and it would still be visible on Earth due to the eclipse completely blocking all solar light. Sir Arthur Eddington performed this experiment in 1919, first measuring the position of the cluster in

January and February (before the eclipse) and then once again during the eclipse. His measurements proved Einstein's theory to be correct, thereby solidifying the scientific community's understanding of how gravity and light interact (Dyson et al., 1920).

When the gravitational field that deflects light is caused by a relatively low-mass object (on the order of stellar masses, rather than galactic masses), the phenomenon is called *microlensing*. When first theorized, Einstein himself predicted that we would be unable to detect microlensing, despite knowing that it was happening (Einstein, 1936). However, today microlensing is not only detectable, but also useful as a powerful scientific tool to study the universe, with applications to the search for extrasolar planets, the quest to understand the nature of dark matter, the study of limb-darkening in stars, the exploration of the structure of the Milky Way's disk, and more.

1.2 Introduction to Microlensing

1.2.1 Microlensing Geometry

Microlensing occurs when the path of light from a light-emitting object is deflected due to the gravitational influence of a massive object; the light-emitting object is called the *source*, and the massive object is called the *lens*.¹ The deflected light then continues on its new path and is ultimately detected by a telescope, called the *observer*. Due to this geometry, there are a greater number of paths along which light from the source can be deflected to reach the observer, and therefore more light reaches the observer, causing the observer to perceive a brightening of the source star. A 2-dimensional representation of this geometry can be seen in Figure 1.1.

If the source were stationary in the sky relative to the lens, the magnification would remain constant, and therefore be undetectable by the observer. However, for microlensing events, the relative proper motion between the source and the lens

¹This section will assume a single-lens system, as the event in question is predicted to be a single-lens system; see Section 1.4.

Figure 1.1: Geometry of Gravitational Lensing

An outline of microlensing geometry, from Wikipedia (2019). Because of how light is bent by gravity, the observer sees two images of the source in the source plane; for microlensing events, these images cannot be resolved by modern telescopes, leading instead to an increase in the observed brightness of the source. D_S is the distance between the observer and the source; for microlensing events, D_S can often be assumed to be about 8 kpc, which is the distance to the galactic bulge from Earth. D_{LS} is the distance between the lens and the source. D_L is the distance between the observer and the lens, and is one of the primary parameters that astronomers seek to determine when analyzing microlensing systems. The angles in this image, while important for understanding microlensing at large, will not be further referenced in this paper and therefore are not discussed at length here.

is non-negligible, and therefore the magnification varies over time. This variation over time can be seen in Figure 1.2, where the magnification of a hypothetical source is plotted over the duration of a hypothetical microlensing event. A plot of the brightness of an object over time, like that shown in Figure 1.2, is called the object's *light curve*. The exact magnitude and duration of the magnification in a microlensing event is determined by the geometry of the source and the lens on the sky. For a discussion of the mathematical parameters describing this geometry, see Section 1.3.

1.2.2 Applications of Microlensing

The magnification of source stars due to microlensing can be used to probe many different areas of astrophysics. One former application of microlensing was as a tool that astrophysicists used to search for specific types of dark matter. A previously

Figure 1.2: Generic Microlensing Light Curve

The black curve represents the magnification of the source of a microlensing event that an observer might see. While the exact peak magnification and width are dependent on the underlying geometry of the system, the general shape of this light curve generalizes to all single-lens microlensing events. This curve shows a microlensing system with $u_0 = 0.1$ and $t_E = 18$ days.

popular theory about the composition of dark matter predicted that dark matter is made of Massive Compact Halo Objects (MACHOs) (Alcock, 1999). If dark matter were indeed concentrated in these massive objects, then these MACHOs would act as microlenses for background stars, and perhaps could be discovered if, for any given event, all other lens types (stars, planets, etc.) could be ruled out. However, microlensing has shown that it is unlikely that dark matter is composed of MACHOs.

Microlensing can also serve as a tool to discover exoplanets around lens stars, as exoplanets' gravitational influence also warps spacetime, thereby altering the observed light curve. Particularly noteworthy about microlensing's ability to discover exoplanets is that it probes a parameter space that is not easily accessed by other exoplanet discovery techniques. Common techniques like the transit method (Winn, 2010) and radial velocity method (Wright, 2018) are biased towards planets that are near their host stars. Moreover, these methods are also biased towards bigger planets; the radial velocity technique is biased towards high-mass planets and the transit

technique is biased towards large-radius planets.

However, microlensing is not subject to the planet “nearness” bias; on the contrary, it is most sensitive to planets at separations between 2-3 au (with decent sensitivity for arbitrarily large separations, though systems with separations greater than $\sim 5 au$ are still relatively hard to detect). Moreover, it has less bias for planet size than the radial velocity and transit methods do. Notably, this provides (when coupled with transits and radial velocities) nearly complete sensitivity to the orbital semi-major axis parameter space out to 5+ au (Barry et al., 2011). Regarding planet size, future microlensing missions are predicted to be sensitive to planets with masses as small as about $0.1 M_{\oplus}$, about an order of magnitude better than the transit and radial velocity methods. This greater sensitivity to planet-mass, coupled with microlensing’s greater planet-star separation sensitivity, allows microlensing surveys to explore in great detail planets that are Earth-like in their size and separation from the Sun. These sensitivities in particular contributed greatly to developing the strategy and goals of the WFIRST mission, scheduled to launch in the mid-2020s.

1.2.3 Objective of This Work

Beyond exoplanets and dark matter, microlensing can also be used to study the components of the galaxy. Under normal conditions, the brightness of an astrophysical object is vitally important in determining its detectability; if an object is too dim, it simply will not be seen by telescopes. However, in microlensing only the brightness of the source star is pertinent to detectability; so long as the source star is bright enough to be observed, the brightness of the lens is immaterial, as only the mass of the lens influences the microlensing system. Therefore, microlensing provides a methodology for studying dim objects in the galaxy, granting unprecedented ability to study dim stars, brown dwarfs, neutron stars, black holes, free-floating planets, and other low-luminosity objects. The most exciting parameters that microlensing can determine about lenses are the mass of the lens, denoted M_L , providing information about what type of object the lens is, and the distance to the lens, denoted D_L ,

allowing astronomers to determine its physical location. Therefore, by analyzing many different microlensing systems, astrophysicists can learn about the true distribution of various populations of astrophysical objects in the galaxy, irrespective of the previously restrictive observing bias of object luminosity.

This thesis seeks to analyze a microlensing system and to report the mass of the lens and distance to the lens of the event. The results of this work will add to the currently known population of lenses studied by microlensing, and therefore contribute to the robustness of population statistics studies of galactic populations.

1.3 Microlensing Parameters

This section details the fundamental microlensing parameters, including discussion of how to determine these parameters via microlensing. While this section does not cover all microlensing parameters, it introduces the ones most pertinent to developing an understanding of microlensing systems and ensures the reader's ability to track the analysis performed later in this thesis.

1.3.1 Parameters From Light Curves

Observations of a microlensing event are in the form of flux measurements at different times. Plotting these flux measurements against the time of the observation returns the light curve. Some of the relevant parameters of microlensing events can be directly determined from the light curve. These parameters are:

- $A(\mathbf{u})$: The defining observable in lensing events is the magnification of the source, denoted $A(u)$, which is determined by:

$$A(u) = \frac{u^2 + 2}{u\sqrt{u^2 + 4}} \quad (1.1)$$

where u is is the time-dependent function:

$$u(t) = \sqrt{u_0^2 + \left(\frac{t - t_0}{t_E}\right)^2} \quad (1.2)$$

Equation (1.2) shows that $u(t)$ is the application of the Pythagorean theorem to the geometry of microlensing events, where u_0 is the time-independent component of the separation on the sky between the source and the lens and $\frac{t-t_0}{t_E}$ is the time-dependent component of the separation on the sky between the source and the lens. Plotting the magnification over time generates a lensing model. Scaling this model to the flux of the source generates the model that coincides with the observed light curve of the microlensing event:

$$f_{model} = f_{source} \times A(u) + f_{blend} \quad (1.3)$$

where f_{model} is the model's final prediction of the flux of the lensed object, f_{source} is the flux that would be observed from the source in the absence of lensing, and f_{blend} accounts for an arbitrary offset in the model.

- **t_0 :** The time of peak magnification in a microlensing event is called t_0 . At this time, the source and lens are as close to each other on the sky as they will ever get, leading to the greatest gravitational effect on the light traveling from the source. It is important to observe microlensing events near the peak of the light curve (meaning around the time of t_0) in order to ensure accurate modeling of the data, which is necessary in order to determine the other parameters of the system. For a discussion of how to estimate t_0 from a light curve, see Section 3.1.
- **u_0 :** The impact parameter of an event, denoted u_0 , describes how close the source and the lens are at the time of closest approach ($t = t_0$). u_0 is normalized by θ_E (see below), such that $u_0 * \theta_E$ is the angular separation on the sky between the lens and the source. Because the magnification of the source (as

viewed by the observer) is correlated with how close the light from the source passes to the lens, this parameter ultimately sets the peak magnification (see Equations (1.1) and (1.2)). For a discussion of how to estimate u_0 from a light curve, see Section 3.2.

- t_E : The Einstein crossing time, denoted t_E , represents the amount of time it takes for the apparent motion of the source (in the frame of a stationary lens) to traverse the Einstein radius. Mathematically, this means that

$$t_E = \frac{\theta_E}{\mu_{rel}} \quad (1.4)$$

where μ_{rel} is the relative proper motion between the source and lens on the sky, and θ_E is the Einstein radius (see below). For a discussion of how to estimate t_E from a light curve, see Section 3.3. Note that while t_E can be determined from the light curve, μ_{rel} and θ_E cannot be. Determining θ_E and μ_{rel} requires further analysis, and therefore these parameters are discussed in greater depth in Section 1.3.2.

1.3.2 Parameters From Further Analysis

While $A(u)$, u_0 , t_0 , and t_E are important for understanding a microlensing system, they themselves are insufficient to accomplish the goal of determining the lens mass and distance to the lens, as laid out in Section 1.2.3. This can be seen in Equations (1.5) and (1.6), which show how to calculate the lens mass and the distance to the lens:

$$M_L = \frac{\theta_E}{\kappa\pi_E} \quad ; \quad (1.5)$$

$$D_L = \frac{1}{\pi_E\theta_E + \frac{1}{D_S}au} au \quad , \quad (1.6)$$

where au denotes the units of a distance term as astronomical units and $\kappa = 8.14 \frac{mas}{M_\odot}$, π_E is the magnitude of the satellite parallax (see below), and θ_E is the Einstein radius (see below). The distance to the source, D_S , is usually assumed to be 8 kpc. This is because microlensing surveys are usually trained on the galactic bulge because that is where the highest density of stars in the galaxy is, and therefore where the greatest number of microlensing events is expected to occur. Therefore, when microlensing events are observed, it is often assumed that the source star is in the galactic bulge because, statistically, it probably is (events with non-bulge sources have very low probability of occurring). Since the distance to the galactic bulge is 8 kpc, D_S is often assumed to be about 8 kpc. Therefore, in order to determine M_L and D_L , either both π_E and θ_E must be determined to solve Equations (1.5) and (1.6), or another method of determining mass-distance relationships that does not rely on one of these parameters must be used. The relevant parameters for determining M_L and D_L are discussed below.

- **θ_E and ρ :** The Einstein radius, denoted θ_E , is the angular radius of the Einstein ring, a mathematical parameter that appears in gravitational lensing equations. It is defined as:

$$\theta_E = \sqrt{\frac{4GM_L}{c^2} \frac{D_S - D_L}{D_S D_L}} \quad (1.7)$$

where G is the gravitational constant, M_L is the lens mass, c is the speed of light, and D_S and D_L are the distances defined in Figure 1.1. In an event with perfect alignment - that is, $u_0 = 0$, such that the lens passes directly in front of the source - the two images of the source would be stretched into a complete circle tracing out the Einstein ring, thereby creating an image with radius θ_E . In non-perfect alignment events, which are predictably the vast majority of lensing events, the size of the Einstein ring serves to set the scale for the event (i.e. parameters like u_0 are reported in units of the Einstein radius).

However, measurable magnification of light from the source does not begin when the source (in the frame of a stationary lens) crosses into the Einstein ring, nor end when it leaves; rather, measurable magnification begins and ends somewhat before and after, respectively, the source crosses the Einstein ring. It is very important for astrophysicists to determine the value of θ_E , because coupling the value of θ_E with the value of the parallax, denoted π_E (see below), or the value of the lens flux, denoted f_L (see below), gives the mass of the source and distance to the source (see Equations (1.5) and (1.6)).

One situation where it is possible to determine the value of θ_E is when the lens passes in front of the source (as seen by the observer). In these events, the observed peak magnification is lower than the predicted peak magnification (of infinity). However, the light curve just before and just after the peak of the event is actually more magnified than if the two objects did not overlap. This leads to a more rounded shape of the peak of the light curve (see Figure 1.3 for an example of these effects). This is due to the finite size of the source on the sky, breaking the modeling assumption that the source is a point-source. In events where finite source effects are observed, the angular size of the source (normalized to units of θ_E), denoted ρ , can often be determined via modeling. ρ is defined as

$$\rho = \frac{\theta_*}{\theta_E} \quad , \quad (1.8)$$

where θ_* is the angular size of the source on the sky. Using the determined value for ρ and Equation (1.8), if θ_* can be determined, then θ_E can be calculated. For a discussion of how to estimate θ_* , see Section 4.2.3. For a discussion of how to estimate ρ from a light curve, see Section 3.4.

- μ_{rel} : After determining θ_E , and with t_E determined from the light curve, the relative lens-source proper motion, denoted μ_{rel} , can be calculated directly from Equation (1.4). Knowing the value of μ_{rel} is particularly useful when

Figure 1.3: Impact of Finite Source Effects on a Microlensing Light Curve

A point-source, point-lens (PSPL) model is the simplest approximation of a microlensing light curve (blue). Finite source effects (FSE, modeled in orange) reduce the peak magnification and widen the peak, but have no measurable impact on the wings of the light curve.

trying to measure the flux from the lens; see below.

- f_L : Though the sources of microlensing events are traditionally much brighter than the lenses (or else the magnification effect would barely be perceptible, rendering the effect nearly undetectable), lens stars can still have measurable fluxes. The lens flux, denoted f_L , can be measured only with high-resolution imaging techniques and if the source star is not particularly bright. It is easier to measure f_L when the source and lens have separated somewhat on the sky, as this makes resolving them a relatively simple task (but also often requires 5-10 years of waiting; see Batista et al. (2015) for one example of calculating the lens flux about a decade after first observing the event). The time that observers must wait before being able to resolve the lens is governed by the size of μ_{rel} . Measurement of the flux of the lens is equivalent to measuring the apparent magnitude of the lens (once corrected for interstellar reddening), denoted m , which provides an absolute magnitude-distance relationship via the distance modulus:

$$m - M = 5 \log_{10} \left(\frac{D_L}{10 \text{ pc}} \right) \quad , \quad (1.9)$$

where M is the absolute magnitude of the lens star and D_L is the distance to the lens star, and pc represents the distance unit of parsecs. By combining this relationship with stellar evolutionary models, which predict a star's luminosity and temperature from its mass, the above magnitude-distance relationship can be converted into a mass-distance relationship. Therefore, obtaining a measurement of f_L can help to determine the mass of the lens and the distance to the lens. Many reported microlensing events, such as Chung et al. (2017), include suggestions that further observations should be taken once the source and lens can be resolved such that f_L can help constrain the measured values for the lens mass and distance to the lens.

- π_E : The Einstein parallax, denoted π_E , governs the difference that observers in different locations would see in the observed position of the source and lens on the sky, and hence the differences that they would observe in the light curve. This parameter can be determined from observations of an event that were made from both an Earth-based telescope and a space-based telescope, or from the non-linear motion of the Earth around the Sun in events with timescales long enough for the non-linearity of the Earth's motion to become significant. The determination of this parameter (particularly its magnitude) is especially valuable given its importance in calculating lens mass and distance (see Equations (1.5) and (1.6)). For a discussion of how to estimate the parallax from two light curves, see Section 3.5.

For a further discussion of the history and formalism of microlensing, see Gaudi (2012) and Gould (2000).

1.4 OGLE-2018-BLG-0705

This thesis reports the mass of, and distance to, the lens of the microlensing event OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 / MOA-2018-BLG-172 / KMT-2018-BLG-1882; for the rest of this thesis, the event will be referred to only by its OGLE name, OGLE-2018-

BLG-0705. The name of the event indicates that it was the 705th event observed by OGLE in 2018 while looking at the galactic bulge (where the bulge is indicated by “BLG”). OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 was observed in July 2018 (8300.5-8331.5 HJD’, where $\text{HJD}' = \text{HJD} - 2450000$), with the peak of the event (as observed from Earth) appearing to fall on July 16th, 2018 (8315.5-8316.5 HJD’; for a more exact date of the event, see Sections 4.1 and 4.3). This event was also observed by Spitzer, with the peak of the event (as observed by Spitzer) appearing to fall around noon (UTC) on July 15th, 2018 (8315.0 HJD’). The source star of this event is Gaia DR2 4065788390847393536. The location on the sky of Gaia DR2 4065788390847393536 (and, hence, OGLE-2018-BLG-0705) is $(\text{RA}, \text{Dec}) = (18:07:11.25, -24:58:56.2)$.

The light curves from Spitzer and Earth (see Figure 3.2) do not show any anomalies indicative of a binary lens, therefore indicating that modeling should begin by assuming that the event is a single-lens event. Given the existence of observations from both Spitzer and ground-based telescopes, the satellite parallax can be calculated for this event. Moreover, a first look at the data reveals a light curve that seems quite likely to have been caused by microlensing influenced by finite source effects, an assumption that is strengthened by reviewing the initial parameter estimates of the event reported by OGLE, MOA, and KMT separately; these estimates can be found in Table 1.1. As Table 1.1 shows, u_0 is estimated to be less than one one-hundredth of the Einstein Radius, which indicates that the source and lens passed very close to each other on the sky, and therefore the angular size of the source would not need to be that large to induce finite source effects. While it is possible for the angular size of the source to in fact be small enough to avoid finite source effects for this value of u_0 , the small value of u_0 taken in concert with the apparent shape of the light curve provide strong evidence that the source passed in front of the lens in OGLE-2018-BLG-0705. Therefore, the light curve indicates that it is possible to determine the mass of the lens and distance to the lens of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 by combining π_E and θ_E , motivating the analysis of this event in the following chapters.

Table 1.1: Initial Parameter Estimates From the Three Microlensing Surveys

Network	t_0 (HJD')	u_0 (units of θ_E)	t_E (days)
OGLE	8316.370	$u_{0,min} = 0.00$	47.683 ± 0.115
KMT	8316.30086	0.008	45.11
MOA	8316.33	0.0022	39.93 ± 0.10

Chapter 2

Data

2.1 Data Sets Used

Observations were made by the Optical Gravitational Lensing Experiment (OGLE) at the Las Campanas Observatory, by the Microlensing Observations in Astronomy project (MOA) at the University of Canterbury Mount John Observatory (UCMJO), by the Korean Microlensing Telescope Network (KMTNet) at the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO), the South African Astronomical Observatory (SAAO), and the Siding Spring Observatory (SSO), by the Microlensing Follow Up Network (μ FUN) at CTIO, the Auckland Observatory (AO), and the Farm Cove Observatory (FCO), by the Las Cumbres Observatory at CTIO and SSO, and by the Spitzer Space Telescope. A summary of the locations, observing bands, and number of observations (denoted N_{obs} is located in Table 2.1. Note: Data points 16-27 from μ FUN’s Auckland observations and 21-26 from Spitzer’s observations were marked as bad by the observers and therefore excluded from the analysis.

MOA’s MOA-specific observing band and the R band both effectively cover the I and V bands, and therefore for limb-darkening considerations (see Section 4.2.3) were considered half I band and half V band. FCO’s unfiltered observations (denoted “U” in Table 2.1) were treated similarly.

Table 2.1: Contributing Data Sets

Network	Observatory	Location	Photometry	Band	N_{obs}
OGLE	Las Campanas	Chile	Magnitude	I	474
KMTNet	SAAO	South Africa	Difference Flux	I	319
KMTNet	CTIO	Chile	Difference Flux	I	552
KMTNet	SSO	Australia	Difference Flux	I	396
μ FUN	CTIO	Chile	Magnitude	I	39
μ FUN	Auckland	New Zealand	Magnitude	R	117
μ FUN	Farm Cove	New Zealand	Magnitude	U	200
Las Cumbres	CTIO	Chile	Difference Flux	I	49
Las Cumbres	SSO	Australia	Difference Flux	I	34
MOA	UCMJO	New Zealand	Difference Flux	MOA	2602
Spitzer	Spitzer	Space	Flux	L	32

2.2 Data Cleaning

2.2.1 Convert Fluxes to Magnitudes

Some data sets report the photons collected by the detectors in fluxes, and others report in magnitudes. In order to model the collected data, it is convenient for all of the data sets to be in magnitude space. There were two different methods of reporting flux data that therefore were converted into magnitudes: data reported as fluxes and data reported as difference fluxes. Table 2.1 shows which data sets were reported in which formats.

Difference flux files report findings in terms of the difference between a reference, high signal-to-noise image, and an image of the same field of view at the given time of recording the observation (Tomaney and Crofts, 1996). This technique is used when the goal is to observe variability in brightness, rather than absolute brightness, and is particularly effective at studying parts of the sky where stars are blended together and hard to individually resolve. The KMTNet and Las Cumbres Network data sets were reported by subtracting the present observation from the reference image, thereby reporting negative difference fluxes (as the microlensing event got brighter, the difference got more negative). The conversion between flux and magnitude involves taking the logarithm of the flux: $m_1 - m_0 = -2.5 \log_{10} \left(\frac{f_1}{f_0} \right)$, where m_1 and f_1 represent the apparent magnitude and flux, respectively, of the star, and m_0 and

f_0 are the apparent magnitude and flux, respectively, of a reference star. Therefore, this would not be mathematically feasible for negative difference fluxes, so first all difference flux values were inverted to positive values.

Then, all of the flux files (difference fluxes and standard fluxes alike) needed to be corrected for any arbitrary offset in the photometry scale that resulted in observations that were negative (in the case of difference flux files, this refers to observations that were newly negative after inverting). This offset was added to each flux data set, and any data points that at this point were still negative were excluded from the analysis. Finally, these data sets were converted into magnitude space.

2.2.2 MOA-Specific Adjustments

The MOA team reported the Julian Dates (JD) of their observations, rather than the Heliocentric Julian Dates (HJD) of the observations like the rest of the observing networks. Therefore, the dates of MOA's observations were adjusted to reflect HJD values.

Moreover, some data points reported by MOA around the peak of the event were over-exposed; while the exposure time for most images taken during this period of time, when the target was particularly bright, was 10 seconds, there were some observations where the exposure time was 60 seconds. All of the 60-second observations from around the peak of the event were removed from the data set due to over-exposure.

Additionally, the peak of the event was so bright that it likely surpassed MOA's saturation limit even for observations with a 10-second exposure time, meaning that MOA could not reliably report the flux values near the peak as the CCD could not record all of the photons that it collected. Therefore, all MOA observations taken between 8316.04-8316.58 HJD' were removed from the data set.

Finally, because MOA reports fluxes on an arbitrary flux scale, both the flux and error values were divided by 6500 at the outset of the analysis in order to obtain

Table 2.2: KMTNet Saturated Data Points

Observatory	Band	Time (HJD')	Bad Points
SSO	I	8313.95 - 8314.20	3
		8315.00 - 8315.15	2
		8315.50 - 8317.50	9
		8318.05 - 8318.10	1
CTIO	I	8314.60 - 8314.85	3
CTIO	I	8316.40 - 8317.90	4
SAAO	I	8317.26 - 8317.27	1

results that are close to calibrated with the other data sets.

2.2.3 Saturation

Most of the stars in the observing fields of the 3 KMTNet telescopes are faint ($I \gtrsim 13$), and therefore the telescopes' pixels can saturate when looking at bright targets. This event became exceptionally bright ($I \sim 10.5$) due to microlensing, leading to saturation concerns. The KMTNet team looked at the initial data files and listed 7 time ranges where all recorded data should be removed due to saturation concerns. These time ranges are listed in Table 2.2. All of these data points were removed from the data sets.

2.2.4 Uncertain Data Points

In addition to some observations being saturated, some observations come with uncertainties that are so large that they are effectively useless for modeling, as we have low confidence that the value that is being reported is actually correct. For this work, any observation with uncertainty of 0.05 magnitudes or more was removed from the data set. This is equivalent to saying that any observation not measured to better than 5% should be discarded. Table 2.3 shows the number of uncertain observations that were removed.

Table 2.3: High-Uncertainty Data Points

Network-Observatory	Uncertain Data Points
OGLE	0
KMTNet-South Africa	1
KMTNet-Chile	2
KMTNet-Australia	3
μ FUN-CTIO	0
μ FUN-Auckland	0
μ FUN-Farm Cove	0
Las Cumbres-CTIO	0
Las Cumbres-SSO	0
MOA	621
Spitzer	0

2.2.5 Sigma Clipping and Error Renormalization

Mathematically, a property of a data set with Gaussian noise is that $\chi_{total}^2 = N$; that is, the average χ^2 per point is 1. Therefore, the goal of this section is to achieve $\chi_{total}^2 = N$ in all data sets. In order to accomplish this, the reported uncertainties need to be adjusted because, unfortunately, for many of these data sets the uncertainties are not reported reliably. Since signal-to-noise for photon noise increases as \sqrt{N} , brighter objects therefore have smaller reported errors. However, there is some brightness value where photon noise loses its status as the dominant noise source, at which point proper uncertainties would account for other sources of systematic error. In addition, the reported uncertainties may be under- or over-reported and therefore need to be re-normalized. This process occurs iteratively with sigma clipping and is described below.

The first step of error renormalization is replacing the reported uncertainties with new uncertainty values calculated in the following way:

$$\sigma_{new} = k \sqrt{\sigma_{old}^2 + \frac{\sigma_{min}^2}{k^2}} \quad (2.1)$$

where the scale factor, k , is defined as

$$k = \sqrt{\frac{\chi_{total}^2}{N}} \quad (2.2)$$

and σ_{min} is a constant that is selected to ensure a more equal distribution of χ^2 across all points in the data set (rather than allowing a few low-uncertainty points to dominate the data set). σ_{min} is bounded by an upper limit of 0.05, as observations with uncertainties much larger than 0.05 are not well enough constrained to be used in modeling (see Section 2.2.4). Note that these equations are valid for magnitudes but not for fluxes.

Additionally, some data points appear to be outliers from the rest of the data set, raising concerns about these points' reliability. All of these points need to be excluded from the data set, despite no clear understanding of why they are misaligned, because an outlier's lack of alignment with the rest of the data set removes confidence in the data point. This is accomplished via sigma clipping.

The first step of sigma clipping is determining which data points are outliers. In order to determine which points are outliers, the value of σ_{clip} must be calculated. σ_{clip} represents the number of standard deviations away from the model beyond which only one good data point is expected to exist. All data points beyond this value of σ_{clip} are then removed from the data set, as statistically only one good data point is expected to be removed, so almost entirely bad data points are removed from the data set. This calculation is shown in the following equation:

$$\frac{N - 1}{N} = erf\left(\frac{\sigma_{clip}}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \quad (2.3)$$

where N is the total number of data points. σ_{clip} is determined using the error function, as $erf\left(\frac{\sigma_{clip}}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$ returns the percent of data points that are expected to be within $\sigma_{clip} * \sigma_{old}$ of the model, where σ_{old} denotes the reported uncertainty in magnitudes. Therefore, solving for σ_{clip} in equation (2.3) returns the value of σ_{clip} . For small data sets this process would result in a small value of σ_{clip} ; therefore, a minimum σ_{clip} of 2.5 is adopted for this analysis, which we apply to all data sets with 80 or fewer observations.

The process for accomplishing simultaneous uncertainty renormalization and

sigma clipping is as follows:

1. Determine the scale factor (k)
2. Determine σ_{new} values, using a pre-selected σ_{min} value
3. Determine σ_{clip}
4. Clip any data point where the residual, denoted δ , satisfies $\delta < (\sigma_{clip} * \sigma_{new})$
5. If no points were cut, the process is over. If some were cut, repeat the process on the remaining data points.

The best σ_{min} value can be determined by performing the above process for a range of σ_{min} values and then comparing the efficacy of each value of σ_{min} at distributing χ^2_{total} across all data points in the set. An example of the results of this iterative process is shown in Figures 2.1 and 2.2, which show the results for the KMTNet Australia (abbreviated “KMT_AI”, where the A stands for Australia and I is the observing band) data set.

Figure 2.1: Clipped Data Points from KMT_AI

The top panels of this figure show all accepted (pink circles) and rejected (red Xs) observations of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 from KMT_AI. The bottom panels show the residuals of each observation. Panels increasingly focus on the peak of the event moving from left to right. KMT_AI is representative of a data set without many points around the peak of the event. While this lack of points around the peak limits the accuracy of model fitting for the given data set, the conditions that must be met for a point to be dropped from the data set are sufficiently loose so as to not inadvertently drop good observations with artificially large deviations from the model arising from poor modeling. While the KMT telescopes were unable to record observations around the peak of this event, other telescopes were able to, ensuring coverage around the peak of the event for later modeling (see Figure 3.1).

Figure 2.2: Convergence of KMT_AI to $\chi_{total}^2 = N$

All observations are sorted by magnification, and the pink curve represents the sum of each point's χ^2 value cumulatively through that point. The black line has slope of 1; therefore, the fact that the pink curve and black line intersect at the last point indicates that the iterative process undertaken in this chapter was successful in establishing $\chi_{total}^2 = N$.

Chapter 3

By-Eye Estimation of Parameters

The goal of this chapter is to determine initial estimates of the parameters of the microlensing system. The determination of these parameters defines a starting point for the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulation that is necessary to determine more precisely the true values of these parameters.

3.1 Estimate of t_0

Estimates for t_0 can be determined directly from a light curve. Since t_0 is the time of peak magnification of the source, and therefore the time of maximum flux, the initial estimate is simply the estimate by eye of what time on the light curve the flux reaches its highest value (or, equivalently, the magnitude reaches its lowest value). As shown in Figure 3.1, this value was estimated to be $t_0 = 8316.3 \text{ HJD}'$.

3.2 Estimate of u_0

An estimate of u_0 can be derived from Equation 1.1. For large magnification events (heuristically anything above $A(u) \approx 10$), u_0 must be small. Also, for small values of u Equation (1.1) reduces to:

Figure 3.1: Peak of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705

The blue line shows the estimated value of $t_0 = 8316.3$ HJD'. The shaded orange region shows an estimate for t_* , representing half of the total time where finite source effects are present in the light curve (the other half immediately precedes the peak).

$$A(u_{small}) = \frac{1}{u_{small}} \quad . \quad (3.1)$$

Therefore, to see a peak magnification of at least 5 magnitudes (as is seen in Figure 3.2), u_0 can be no larger than 0.01, since 5 magnitudes is equivalent to an increase in brightness by a factor of 100, and $\frac{1}{0.01} = 100$. Since Figure 3.2 indicates roughly $\Delta m \approx 5.25$, that gives $A(u) \sim 125$, and from Equation (3.1) that gives $u_0 = 0.008$.

It is worth noting that if finite source effects are proven to impact this light curve (as at this point would be expected; see Section 3.4), then the peak magnification of the light curve will not reflect the approximation in Equation (3.1), as finite source effects limit the peak magnification of an event (see Figure 1.3). Therefore, proven finite source effects would indicate a smaller value of u_0 , making $u_0 = 0.008$ represent an upper bound on u_0 ; see Section 4.2 for further discussion of the impact of finite source effects on OGLE-2018-BLG-0705.

3.3 Estimate of t_E

The Einstein crossing time represents the time it takes the source (in the frame of a stationary lens) to cross the radius of the Einstein ring. While the Einstein ring is important in the underlying geometry of a microlensing system, it does not represent the region where observable source-magnification begins; this happens well before the source is observed to cross the Einstein ring. The expected magnification at the time of crossing the Einstein ring can be determined from Equations (1.1) and (1.2).

$u(t)$ is normalized by the Einstein ring radius such that $u(t_0 \pm t_E) = 1$ (assuming zero impact parameter for simpler calculations – breaking this assumption only corrects for more complicated geometries, but does not change the derived results). Therefore, when the source crosses the Einstein ring ($t = t_0 \pm t_E$), the expected magnification is:

$$A(1) = \frac{1^2 + 2}{1 * \sqrt{1^2 + 4}} = \frac{3}{\sqrt{5}} \approx 1.34 \quad (3.2)$$

The change in apparent magnitude for different fluxes is given by:

$$\Delta m = 2.5 \times \log \left(\frac{f_2}{f_1} \right) \quad (3.3)$$

where f_i is the i th flux measurement. Plugging in a flux ratio of 1.34 returns $\Delta m = 2.5 \times \log(1.34) \approx 0.3$. Therefore, the time between magnification of 0.3 magnitudes and t_0 is the estimate of t_E . From Figure 3.2, t_E was estimated to be $t_E = 45$ days.

Figure 3.2: Light curve of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705

The blue line shows where magnification is 0.3 magnitudes above the baseline, which itself is shown in black. The green shaded region indicates the estimate of t_E , which is the time between magnification of 1.34 (increase in 0.3 magnitudes) and the peak of the event. t_E was estimated to be $t_E = 45$ days.

3.4 Estimate of ρ

The parameter ρ represents the angular size of the source on the sky, normalized by the angular size of the Einstein Ring. That is,

$$\rho = \frac{\theta_*}{\theta_E} \quad . \quad (3.4)$$

These θ values can be converted into times, because the time it takes to cross either distance is simply $t_i = \frac{\theta_i}{\mu_{rel}}$, where μ_{rel} is the proper motion of the source relative to the lens. This gives:

$$\rho = \frac{\theta_*}{\theta_E} = \frac{t_* * \mu_{rel}}{t_E * \mu_{rel}} = \frac{t_*}{t_E} \quad . \quad (3.5)$$

ρ can therefore be determined from the light curve because finite source effects lead to a rounding of the peak of the light curve, as seen in Figure 3.1. Therefore, the time it takes to cross this rounded peak region is $2t_*$, where t_* is the time it takes for the radius of the source to cross the lens (in the frame of a stationary lens). For

this reason, half of the width of this rounded part can be estimated to be t_* . This region is shown in Figure 3.1, giving $t_* \approx 0.5$ days. Combining the estimates of t_* and t_E gives an estimate for ρ :

$$\rho = \frac{t_*}{t_E} \approx \frac{0.5}{45} = \boxed{0.011 \approx \rho} \quad (3.6)$$

This calculated value for ρ is consistent with other assumptions about the system. For finite source effects to be relevant in an event's light curve, ρ must be comparable to or greater than u_0 ; otherwise, the lens and source will not overlap on the sky and the assumption of a point-source will properly model a point-lens system. Since Figure 3.1 shows a rounded peak consistent with a source experiencing finite source effects, the parameter estimates from the light curve should show $\rho > u_0$, and indeed, $0.011 > 0.008$, so the estimates are consistent with predictions thus far.

3.5 Estimate of π_E

3.5.1 Degeneracies in π_E

The microlensing parallax, π_E , is the measured parallax of the system in two components, π_{EN} (North) and π_{EE} (East), on the sky. This value explains the difference in the orientation of the 3 objects (lens, source, observer) of the system when viewed from Earth from when viewed from a satellite, which leads to differences in the observed light curve. In the case of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705, the satellite observations were made by Spitzer. However, the determination of π_E is subject to a four-fold degeneracy - two-fold in magnitude and two-fold in direction. These degeneracies result from the fact that multiple orientations of the source-lens system can return identical Earth / satellite light curves. Figure 3.3 shows these four different orientations that lead to the same light curves, and hence the degeneracies.

The cause of these degeneracies can be found in Equations (1.1) and (1.2). Since $u(t)$ is always positive (because it is a square root of a sum of squares), $A(u)$ is

Figure 3.3: Lens-Source Degenerate Orientations

This image (adapted from Gould (1994a)) shows the different orientations of a microlensing event from Earth and a satellite that would result in the same observed light curves. The solid line in each figure is the trajectory of the source (in the frame of a stationary lens) as seen from Earth, and the dashed line is the trajectory of the source as seen from the satellite. The black dot represents the lens. Δu is as it is defined in Equation (3.7). The two-fold degeneracy in magnitude of π_E appears because Panels (a) and (d) share the magnitude of Δu , and so do Panels (b) and (c) (see Equation (3.8)).

also always positive. However, u_0 can be either positive or negative (implying an impact parameter where the source is either above or below the lens, respectively) and still return the same value of $u(t)$ (and, therefore, $A(u)$) since u_0 is squared in Equation (1.2). Moreover, when analyzing two light curves (as is the case when studying satellite parallax), both $u_{0,Earth}$ and $u_{0,sat}$ can be positive or negative, creating a four-fold degeneracy. As shown in Figure 3.3, this manifests in a two-fold degeneracy in the magnitude of π_E and a two-fold degeneracy in the direction of π_E .

The difference in $u(t)$ between the view of the system from the ground and from

the satellite is what π_E measures. The equation for this difference is shown below:

$$\Delta u_{\pm} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{t_{0,Earth} - t_{0,sat}}{t_E}\right)^2 + (\Delta u_{0,\pm})^2} \quad ; \quad (3.7)$$

$$\Delta u_{0,\pm} = |u_{0,Earth} \pm u_{0,sat}| \quad . \quad (3.8)$$

Equation (3.7) is derived from Equation (1.2), which is the standard equation for $u(t)$, by accounting for changes in either u_0 or t_0 across the light curves, which are the two components of $u(t)$. Δu_{\pm} is the change in $u(t)$ between the light curve that is viewed from Earth and the light curve viewed from the satellite. The "±" in the subscript denotes the two-fold degeneracy in direction, since the square-root in Equation (3.7) gives Δu the ability to be either positive or negative. $\Delta u_{0,\pm}$ is the difference between $u_{0,Earth}$ and $u_{0,sat}$, as shown in Equation (3.8). $\Delta u_{0,-}$ corresponds to the smaller possible value of Δu_0 , which would be Figures 3.3a and 3.3d, and $\Delta u_{0,+}$ corresponds to the larger possible value, shown in Figures 3.3b and 3.3c. The different possible values for Δu_0 lead to two different magnitudes of Δu_{\pm} , represented by the subscript, generating the two-fold degeneracy in magnitude. Therefore, there is a four-fold degeneracy in π_E from the light curve alone.

In many calculations only the magnitude of π_E is relevant; for example, when solving for the mass of the lens or the distance to the lens, only the magnitude of π_E affects the resulting values, not the direction. Therefore, in some situations the only degeneracy that needs to be broken in order to get singular results is that in magnitude. Gould and Yee (2012) showed that for particularly high-magnification events (heuristically $A(u) > 100$) the difference in the magnitude of π_E is so small that it can be ignored. This can be seen in equation (3.8) where a large magnification (which implies a small $u_{0,Earth}$) must lead to a small difference between $\Delta u_{0,+}$ and $\Delta u_{0,-}$, given the possible geometries discussed above.

An approximation (assuming rectilinear motion of the Earth and satellite) of the

components of $\boldsymbol{\pi}_E$ is given by Refsdal (1966):

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}_E = \frac{au}{D_\perp} \left(\frac{\Delta t_0}{t_E}, \Delta u_0 \right) \quad (3.9)$$

where D_\perp is the projected separation vector between the Earth and Spitzer in the plane of the sky, which, at the time of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705, was approximately equal to 1.65 *au*. t_E is roughly constant across both satellite and ground-based observations, as this should not change much based on which telescope observed the event (the Einstein ring radius does not change for the event because the Einstein ring radius is determined by the gravitational strength of the lens and not the geometry of the system; neither does the relative source-lens proper motion change appreciably, so the time to cross the Einstein ring should remain roughly constant across different observing locations - see Equation (1.4)). Note, this approximation is simply the vector-component form of Equation (3.7), linking the above discussion of degeneracies to direct calculation of $\boldsymbol{\pi}_E$. For further discussion of how to break the microlensing parallax degeneracies, see Gould (2013), Yee (2013), Calchi Novati et al. (2015), and Yee et al. (2015).

3.5.2 Estimating $\boldsymbol{\pi}_E$

The parallax is related to the mass and distance of the lens via Equations (1.5) and (1.6). Importantly, since u_0 is estimated to be less than 0.01, the event is expected to be large-enough magnification that the magnitude degeneracy in $\boldsymbol{\pi}_E$ becomes insignificant. This means that the system should contain enough information for singular determination of the lens mass and lens distance from parallax, despite the degeneracies in $\boldsymbol{\pi}_E$. However, even though the direction degeneracy is not immediately relevant for calculating M_L and D_L , see Section 5.3 for a resolution of the direction degeneracy in $\boldsymbol{\pi}_E$ for OGLE-2018-BLG-0705.

Equation (3.9) gives an approximation for calculating $\boldsymbol{\pi}_E$, which can be estimated strictly from the light curve. Δt_0 can be approximated by eye by estimating

Figure 3.4: Spitzer Photometry for OGLE-2018-BLG-0705

Spitzer light curve for the event. The blue line represents the estimated t_0 value for the Spitzer light curve. The gap in observations between 8321 HJD' and 8326 HJD' reflects the removal of bad data points resulting from photometric issues with Spitzer on those days.

t_0 for the Spitzer light curve in the same way as was done with ground-based observations in Section 3.1. The initial estimate for $t_{0,sat}$ is $t_{0,sat} = 8315.0$ HJD' (as shown in Figure 3.4). Δu_0 cannot be approximated by attempting to infer the relation between magnification and u_0 from the light curve, as was done in Section 3.2, because observations of the event from Spitzer were stopped before the event had returned to baseline. Instead, the Spitzer observations were modeled by an MCMC which held t_E constant, using the estimate from ground-based observations, and let $t_{0,sat}$ and $u_{0,sat}$ be free parameters. This returned an estimate for $u_{0,sat}$ to be $u_{0,sat} = 0.384$. Comparing these values to the values obtained in Sections 3.1 and 3.2 for ground-based observations gives the parameters needed to estimate $\boldsymbol{\pi}_E$. That is:

$$\Delta t_0 = 8315.0 - 8316.3 = -1.3 \text{ days} \quad , \quad \Delta u_0 = 0.384 - 0.008 = 0.375 \quad (3.10)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}_E = \frac{au}{1.65 au} \left(\frac{-1.3}{45}, 0.375 \right) = \boxed{(-0.018, 0.228)} = \boldsymbol{\pi}_E \quad (3.11)$$

Chapter 4

Analysis and Modeling

This chapter covers all preparatory work needed to run reliable MCMC simulations and then reports the results from these simulations.

4.1 MCMC to Determine Initial Values of Ground-Based Parameters

The estimates of t_0 , t_E , u_0 , and ρ from the previous chapter specified the starting point for a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulation that would determine more precisely the best values for the microlensing parameters of the ground-based observations. Because the goal of this MCMC is to determine precise values of the microlensing parameters for ground-based observations, Spitzer observations (and therefore the estimate of the parallax from Section 3.5) were left out of the initial MCMC. Having the results from this MCMC will allow for a better determination of the parallax from further MCMC runs that include the parallax as a free parameter, as there will be less variance in the above four parameters during these further MCMC runs, allowing the MCMC to optimize more for the parallax.

All ground-based data sets were incorporated into this MCMC, the results of which are shown in Table 4.1. The results of the MCMC are very similar to the predicted values from Chapter 3, with the exception of u_0 . However, the estimate

Table 4.1: Results From the First MCMC Run

Parameter	Light Curve Estimate	MCMC Result
t_0 (HJD')	8316.3	8316.3140 ± 0.0001
u_0	0.008	0.00248 ± 0.00005
t_E (Days)	45	46.2 ± 0.1
ρ	0.011	0.01055 ± 0.00002

of u_0 in Section 3.2 was expected to be too large due to the presence of finite source effects in the light curve, since finite source effects reduce the peak magnification of the source, which, in turn, increases the predicted value of u_0 (see Equation (3.1)). Therefore, the MCMC derived result for u_0 is also consistent with predictions from Chapter 3, despite the discrepancy between the predicted and calculated values.

4.2 Finite Source Effects

4.2.1 Selecting the FSE / Non-FSE Modeling Cutoff

Modeling of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 was performed using the `MulensModel` code (Poleski and Yee, 2018). As discussed in Section 4.1, the data seem to contain finite source effects, which can be accounted for by the `MulensModel` package, but at the expense of significantly increased computing time in MCMCs. Therefore, modeling in the `MulensModel` code must at some point switch from point-source, point-lens modeling (see Figure 1.3) to modeling with finite source effects. At this point, the algorithm must begin modeling with the methodology outlined in Gould (1994b). Therefore, it is important to determine a value where the modeling algorithms can be switched that accounts for both computing time and modeling precision considerations.

In order to make this determination, two models were made across the duration of the event, each with the same initial parameter values for t_0 , u_0 , t_E , and ρ that were calculated in Section 4.1. One of these models was generated using the standard PSPL modeling algorithm, and the other model was generated using the Gould (1994b) algorithm. Then, the percent change between the two models was calculated

for each point in time, and the times where the percent change was calculated to be less than 0.05% were determined. The total number of days between these two points is equal to the number of days that need to be calculated with the finite source effects algorithm instead of the standard PSPL algorithm.

The percent change cutoff value of 0.05% was chosen because it represents a value where the error induced by using the PSPL algorithm is dwarfed by the average error in the data. This determination relies on the relation that $\sigma_{mag} \approx \frac{\sigma_{flux}}{flux}$. This relation can be derived by beginning with the equation for apparent magnitude, performing a change of base to natural logarithms, taking the derivative of both sides, and then isolating Δm , as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 m &= -2.5 \log_{10} f + C \quad , \quad \log_{10} f = \frac{\ln f}{\ln 10} \approx \frac{\ln f}{2.3} \\
 m &= -\frac{2.5}{2.3} \ln f + C \\
 \frac{dm}{df} &\approx \frac{-2.5}{2.3f} = \frac{1.09}{f} \\
 dm &= 1.09 \frac{df}{f} \\
 \boxed{\sigma_{mag} = 1.09 \frac{\Delta f}{f} \approx \frac{\sigma_{flux}}{f}} & \tag{4.1}
 \end{aligned}$$

where f represents flux, m represents apparent magnitude, and σ_i represents the error in the variable in its subscript, denoted i . Using this relation, it can be determined that a 0.01 magnitude uncertainty is approximately equivalent to a 1% uncertainty. The OGLE data set has a mean error in magnitude of 0.005, and other data sets have mean errors of similar size. This is equivalent to a 0.5% error. Therefore, the selected cutoff point of introducing a 0.05% error to the models is a proper one, as this introduced error will be dwarfed by the existing noise in the data, which is an order of magnitude greater. It is for this reason that 0.05% was chosen as the cutoff point.

Using this cutoff point for where the models become indistinguishable, t_{switch} was determined to be 3.12 days, where everything between $[t_0 - t_{switch}, t_0 + t_{switch}]$

was modeled with the finite source effects algorithm and everything outside of this time range was modeled with the standard PSPL algorithm.

4.2.2 Does Spitzer Have FSEs?

In order to determine whether Spitzer observed a light curve with finite source effects, the Spitzer light curve (absent ground-based data) was fit to a model with the initial parameter values of $t_E = 46.2$ days, $t_0 = 8315.0$ HJD', and $u_0 = 0.008$. The t_E value was determined from the initial ground-based observations MCMC run (as discussed in Section 4.1), since the value of t_E is expected to be roughly constant for both ground-based and space-based observations (see Section 3.5). The t_0 value was determined by eye from viewing the Spitzer light curve (see Figure 3.4) and estimating at what date the light curve reached its maximum (see Section 3.5).

The u_0 value was determined by using the same initial estimate from Section 3.2; the MCMC-returned value from Section 4.1 could not be used because, unlike t_E , u_0 changes drastically between data sets with and without finite source effects (as the magnitude of u_0 directly determines if finite source effects appear in the light curve). Therefore, it was assumed that if there are finite source effects then u_0 must be similar to the value obtained from ground-based observations since u_0 would still have to be less than $\rho \approx 0.01$. If there are not finite source effects, then this MCMC will return a larger value of u_0 .

Another way of selecting the initial value for u_0 is to use the estimated value of $u_{0,sat}$ that was determined in Section 3.5.2, which was 0.384. However, given knowledge of the approximate size of ρ (from Section 4.1) such that $\rho < 0.384$, selecting this value initializes the MCMC in the parameter space without finite source effects. A more robust proof that finite source effects do not appear in the Spitzer light curve (as is expected given this estimate of u_0) is to initialize the MCMC with a u_0 value such that finite source effects would need to be taken into account. If the resulting MCMC determined that u_0 must be much larger than its initialized value, then finite source effects are not present in the light curve. Therefore, the

starting value of u_0 for this run was chosen as 0.008, the same as was done for modeling the ground-based data.

Since t_0 and u_0 are expected to be different in the Spitzer light curve than in the ground-based light curve, these two parameters are left as free parameters. However, since t_E is expected to be roughly constant in both light curves, t_E was fixed in this run. ρ is not included in this MCMC run because the point of the run is to determine whether ρ is a relevant parameter or not. If the results of this run indicate that u_0 is small, then a subsequent MCMC run would introduce ρ to account for the discovered finite source effects.

The best values for t_0 and u_0 returned by this MCMC are:

$$t_{0,sat} = 8315.0563 \text{ HJD}' \quad , \quad u_{0,sat} = 0.335 \quad .$$

The MCMC clearly returned $u_{0,sat} \gg \rho_{ground}$, indicating that the Spitzer data does not contain finite source effects. Therefore, further modeling with the Spitzer data does not account for finite source effects. Further modeling of ground-based data of course still accounts for finite source effects, as ρ_{ground} was shown to be significant in Section 4.1.

4.2.3 Source Properties

In microlensing events with finite source effects, the assumption of a point-source that is often used in microlensing modeling breaks down, and instead modeling must take into account the finite size of the source object on the sky. In particular, this means accounting for limb-darkening, or the non-uniform brightness across the surface of the source. Limb-darkening can be parameterized in many different ways; in this thesis, we used the linear limb-darkening law. For a discussion of the different limb-darkening laws, see Magic, Z. et al. (2015).

In order to obtain appropriate limb-darkening coefficients for the I and V observing bands, the effective temperature, denoted T_{eff} , needs to be determined. This

can be accomplished if the (V-I) color of the source star is known, because Bessell and Brett (1988) gives conversions from (V-I) to T_{eff} .

Locating the source star on a color-magnitude diagram can help to determine the color of the source. Moreover, the source star's location on a color-magnitude diagram can help to determine θ_* . This is because certain stellar populations on a CMD are standard candles, meaning that their intrinsic luminosity and color are known. Therefore, by adding the offset between the measured color of the stellar population and the measured color of the source star to the population's intrinsic color value, the true color of the source star can be determined. That is, $(V-I)_{clump} - (V-I)_{source} = \Delta(V-I)$, and $(V-I)_{0,clump} + \Delta(V-I) = (V-I)_{0,source}$.

As shown in Figure 4.1, the source star appears on a color-magnitude diagram in the region of the Red Clump. The Red Clump population are known to have a $(V-I)_0$ color of 1.06 (Bensby et al., 2011).

The clump centroid (I-H) and I-band values were determined to be $(I-H, I)_{clump} = (3.570, 17.4)$. This gives the difference between the clump and the source:

$$\Delta(I-H, I) = (I-H, I)_S - (I-H, I)_{clump} = (0.229, -1.209) \quad (4.2)$$

Given the right ascension and declination of the event (see Section 1.4), the distance to the clump can be calculated to be $D_{cl} = 7.6 \text{ kpc} \pm 1$ and the intrinsic I-band magnitude of clump is found to be $I_{cl,0} = 14.28$ (Nataf et al., 2013). From relations for giant stars found in Bessell and Brett (1988), Kervella et al. (2004), and the calculated values above, the following results can be obtained:

$$I_{S,0} = I_{cl,0} + \Delta I = 14.28 - 1.209 = 13.071$$

$$(V-I)_{S,0} = 1.389 \text{ (Bessell and Brett (1988) Relation)}$$

$$\theta_* = 14.63 \mu\text{as} \text{ (Kervella et al. (2004) Relation)}$$

We assumed a 7% error in θ_* , consistent with calculations considering $(V-I) \pm \sigma_{(V-I)}$, giving $\theta_* = 14.63 \mu\text{as} \pm 1.02 \mu\text{as}$. The determination of θ_* is needed to

Figure 4.1: Color-Magnitude Diagram in the Stellar Neighborhood of the Event

This color-magnitude diagram represents the field stars in the same region of the sky as OGLE-2018-BLG-0705. The stars in the field are from VVV observations and CT13 H-band observations (converted to VVV magnitudes). The red dot denotes the centroid of the Red Clump ($(I - H, I)_{cl} = (3.570, 17.4)$), and the blue square denotes the source star of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705. From the CMD, the source star can be seen to be a part of the Red Clump, whose intrinsic $(V-I)$ color is 1.06.

calculate θ_E ; see Section 5.1 for this calculation.

Then, to get the true value of T_{eff} for the source, we assume similar properties for OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 as for stars in Baade’s Window (a particular region on the sky looking at the bulge where the reddening is well understood). Although OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 does not reside in Baade’s Window, it also is in the direction of the galactic bulge, and so we assume that the stars in Baade’s Window are a good approximation for bulge stars in general.

Zoccali et al. (2008) estimates the stellar parameters (observed $(V-I)$, T_{eff} , $\log(g)$, and microturbulent velocity, denoted v_t) for the stars in Baade’s window. Using the known extinction correction from Nataf et al. (2013), the observed $(V-I)$ can be converted into the intrinsic $(V-I)_0$ value of these stars. Since the source star

is expected to be a similar type star to these giants, the properties of the source star can be inferred from these values. From these papers, the source star is predicted to have effective temperature $T_{eff} \approx 4400$ K, $\log(g) \approx 2.4$, and microturbulent velocity $v_t \approx 1.4$ km/s. With these values in hand, and the assumption of solar metallicity, limb-darkening coefficients were derived from Claret (2000). The I and V band results were:

$$u_I = 0.6444 \quad u_V = 0.8291$$

where u_X is the limb-darkening coefficient for the X observing band. These values were used in all modeling of ground-based observations for this thesis. Note, Claret (2000) only reports limb-darkening coefficients for specific values of stellar parameters, so some inferred parameters were rounded to the nearest value for which Claret (2000) reports results that remained consistent with comparisons to stars in Baade’s Window.

4.3 Final MCMC Fitting

With limb-darkening coefficients determined and the knowledge that Spitzer’s light curve does not exhibit finite source effects, full MCMCs can be run fitting both ground-based and space-based observations together. These runs should further refine the values of t_0 , u_0 , t_E , and ρ , and reveal the values of π_{EE} and π_{EN} . The four runs performed were initialized with parameters consistent with the degeneracies discussed in Section 3.5.1, such that all four solutions could be found by the MCMCs. The results of these MCMCs are summarized in the yellow rows of Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Results for the 4 Degenerate MCMC Solutions ($\pm u_0, \pm \pi_{EN}$)

Parameter	Run #1: (-, +)	Run #2: (+, -)	Run #3: (-, -)	Run #4: (+, +)
t_0 (HJD')	8316.3135 ± 0.0001	8316.3135 ± 0.0001	8316.3134 ± 0.0001	8316.3135 ± 0.0001
u_0	-0.00230 ± 0.00004	0.00230 ± 0.00005	-0.00229 ± 0.00005	0.00227 ± 0.00005
t_E (Days)	46.2 ± 0.1	46.2 ± 0.1	46.2 ± 0.1	46.2 ± 0.1
ρ	0.01050 ± 0.00003	0.01050 ± 0.00003	0.01050 ± 0.00003	0.01050 ± 0.00002
π_{EN}	0.226 ± 0.002	-0.234 ± 0.002	-0.230 ± 0.002	0.225 ± 0.002
π_{EE}	-0.0241 ± 0.0007	-0.0091 ± 0.0005	-0.0087 ± 0.0005	-0.0265 ± 0.0005
μ_{rel} (mas/yr)	11.0 ± 0.8	11.0 ± 0.8	11.0 ± 0.8	11.0 ± 0.8
π_E	0.228 ± 0.002	0.234 ± 0.002	0.231 ± 0.002	0.226 ± 0.002
θ_E (mas)	1.39 ± 0.10	1.39 ± 0.10	1.39 ± 0.10	1.39 ± 0.10
M_L (M_\odot)	0.75 ± 0.05	0.73 ± 0.05	0.74 ± 0.05	0.76 ± 0.05
D_L (kpc)	2.2 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.1

Parameters determined by the MCMC are highlighted in yellow.
 Parameters derived from further analysis are highlighted in blue.

Chapter 5

Results and Conclusions

5.1 Determining Derived Parameters

With θ_* determined to be $14.63 \mu\text{as}$, it is possible to calculate θ_E , which, as discussed earlier, is one of the critical parameters for calculating the mass of the lens and the distance to the lens. This can be accomplished by utilizing the final MCMC results. The below calculations utilize the results from Run #1. The results of performing these calculations for the other runs are nearly identical and can be found in the blue-highlighted portion of Table 4.2. In Run #1, $\rho = 0.0105$. Combining the value of θ_* with the estimate of ρ from Run #1 gives θ_E ; therefore, θ_E is found to be:

$$\theta_E = \frac{\theta_*}{\rho} = \frac{14.63 \mu\text{as}}{0.0105} = \boxed{1.39 \text{ mas}}$$

With θ_E calculated, all that is needed to get the mass of the lens and distance to the lens is π_E . Since π_{EN} and π_{EE} were determined by the MCMC, the value for π_E (for the first run) is:

$$\pi_E = \sqrt{\pi_{EN}^2 + \pi_{EE}^2} = \sqrt{0.226^2 + (-0.0241)^2} = 0.228 \quad . \quad (5.1)$$

Figure 5.1: Mass and Distance Relations for θ_E and π_E , Run #1

The black curve shows the mass-distance relationship given by the microlensing parallax, with one-sigma and two-sigma uncertainties shown in the dashed black lines. The blue curve represents the mass-distance relationship given from finite source effects, also with one- and two-sigma uncertainties shown. The relationship from finite source effects is less well constrained than the relationship from parallax. M_L and D_L are determined by the intersection of the two curves, denoted by the green star. The distance to NGC 6544, the likely host cluster of the lens star (see Section 5.3), is shown on the plot as a vertical red line, with 1-sigma uncertainty shown by the red-shaded region.

The calculated values for π_E and θ_E , and therefore M_L and D_L , for each MCMC run are listed in the blue-highlighted portion of Table 4.2. Figure 5.1 shows the mass vs. distance relationships that were used to determine these values for Run #1, illustrating how the mass-distance relationships that θ_E and π_E provide return calculated values of M_L and D_L . The same figures for Runs #2-4 are nearly identical to Figure 5.1 (because the π_E degeneracy in magnitude is negligible) and therefore are not shown here.

Additionally, Equation (1.4) shows that $\mu_{rel} = \frac{\theta_E}{t_E}$. Therefore, coupling the above derivation of θ_E with the t_E values returned from the MCMC allows μ_{rel} to be calculated as well. These μ_{rel} values are also given in the blue-highlighted portion of Table 4.2.

5.2 NGC 6544

NGC 6544, shown in Figure 5.2, is a star cluster in the same observing field as OGLE-2018-BLG-0705. NGC 6544 is a $115,000 M_{\odot}$ cluster residing $2.6 \pm 0.27 \text{ kpc}^1$ away from Earth with metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.40$ (Baumgardt et al., 2019; Nataf et al., 2019). It has a $126''$ tidal radius on the sky (Baumgardt et al., 2019), which can be converted to a physical radius size via the equation for angular size:

$$\theta = \frac{R}{d} \quad (5.2)$$

where R is the physical radius of the object in au , d is the distance to the object in parsecs, and θ is the angular size on the sky in arcseconds. This gives:

$$126'' \times 2600\text{pc} = R_{cluster} = 1.6\text{pc} \quad .$$

NGC 6544's exact location on the sky is $(\text{RA}, \text{Dec}) = (271.835750, -24.997333)$, which is $138''$ away from OGLE-2018-BLG-0705. This angular separation places OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 just beyond where the gravitational influence of the cluster dominates the gravitational influence of the galaxy. This leaves open the possibility that the lens of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 is a part of the population of cluster stars and is located at the outskirts of the cluster. Figure 5.1 shows that at just beyond the 1-sigma level it is possible that these objects are at the same distance from Earth. While this is not on its own strong evidence that the lens is in NGC 6544, this would act as good supporting evidence for a different, stronger claim that the lens was in NGC 6544. Therefore, further exploration is warranted.

¹This value is an average of the listed distances from the 2010 update to Harris (1996) and Baumgardt et al. (2019), the latter of which was derived using Gaia proper motions.

Figure 5.2: Image of NGC 6544

This image from the second generation Digital Sky Survey is centered at (RA, Dec) = (271.835750, -24.997333), which is the location of NGC 6544. The yellow circle denotes the tidal radius of the cluster ($r_{\text{tidal}} = 126''$). The green star is placed at (RA, Dec) = (271.796875, -24.9823), which is the location of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 on the sky, $138''$ from the center of the cluster.

5.3 Is the Lens in NGC 6544?

To determine if the lens star is truly in the cluster, the Gaia DR2 proper motions of all stars in the observing field (Figure 5.2²) were plotted in Figure 5.3. Two clear regions appear in the plot: the upper grouping of mostly bulge stars and the lower grouping of mostly NGC 6544 stars. The clear difference in proper motion between the two populations allows for the characterization of the lens star, so long as the proper motion of the lens star can be calculated. This can be accomplished by combining the Gaia proper motion of the source star (from Gaia Collaboration (2018)³) with the determined value of μ_{rel} , corrected to the heliocentric relative

²The Digitized Sky Survey was produced at the Space Telescope Science Institute under U.S. Government grant NAG W-2166. The images of these surveys are based on photographic data obtained using the Oschin Schmidt Telescope on Palomar Mountain and the UK Schmidt Telescope. The plates were processed into the present compressed digital form with the permission of these institutions.

³The proper motion of the source is mildly corrupted because Gaia measures the combined proper motion of the source and the lens, with reported noise of 1.44 mas/yr. However, incorporating error at this level would not change the derived results.

proper motion, via the following equations (e.g. Ryu et al. (2020)):

$$\mu_{hel} = \mu_{rel} \hat{\pi}_E + \frac{\pi_{rel}}{au} \mathbf{v}_{\oplus, \perp} \quad ; \quad (5.3)$$

$$\mu_{source} + \mu_{hel} = \mu_{lens} \quad , \quad (5.4)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_{\oplus, \perp}$ is the Earth's velocity projected on the event at t_0 .

As Figure 5.3 shows, the lens star is likely in the cluster. This determination was made because solutions with negative values of π_{EN} lead to a value of μ_{lens} consistent with those in the population of NGC 6544 stars, within 3-sigma of the reported cluster proper motion (as shown by the blue star's existence in the purple shaded region of the figure). A positive value of π_{EN} would have placed the lens beyond the grouping of the bulge stars, which would be unlikely even if there were not other evidence that the lens might reside in NGC 6544. By contrasting the strong alignment of the proper motions when π_{EN} is negative with the seemingly unlikely result when π_{EN} is positive, it can be stated with reasonable confidence that the lens star of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 does reside in NGC 6544. Moreover, this fact allows for the breaking of one of the degeneracies in $\boldsymbol{\pi}_E$, as the direction of π_{EN} has been determined with reasonable confidence, thereby breaking the two-fold degeneracy in direction.

The determination of the sign of π_{EN} removes the MCMC results from Run #1 and Run #4 from consideration as the true solution, leaving only a two-fold degeneracy between Run #2 and Run #3; these runs have nearly identical magnitudes of $\boldsymbol{\pi}_E$, as predicted by Gould and Yee (2012). This manifests in nearly identical 1-sigma confidence intervals for both M_L and D_L in Run #2 and Run #3. Therefore, for all intents and purposes, all $\boldsymbol{\pi}_E$ degeneracies in the OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 system have been resolved.

The fact that the lens of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 appears to belong to NGC 6544 raises the question of whether the reported distance to NGC 6544 is over-estimated, as the calculation of D_L in this paper is quite tight (uncertainty of 0.1 kpc) as

compared with the quoted distance to NGC 6544 in Baumgardt et al. (2019) (uncertainty of 0.27 kpc). Moreover, previous estimates of the distance to NGC 6544 were lower than the value that Gaia arrived at (see Harris (1996)), providing further reason to suspect that Gaia DR2 over-estimated the distance to the cluster. As the Gaia team releases more data, it is worth tracking if the determined distance to NGC 6544 is ultimately revised to a value more in line with the one calculated in this thesis.

5.4 Concluding Thoughts

This thesis reports a roughly $0.74 \pm 0.05 M_{\odot}$ star 2.2 ± 0.1 kpc away from Earth in the direction of the galactic bulge discovered via microlensing. Determining the physical properties of the lens star was only possible because observations of the microlensing event were made both by ground-based telescopes and the Spitzer Space Telescope, and because the ground-based observations exhibited finite source effects in the light curve. The reported lens star is likely to be in the outskirts of the star cluster NGC 6544. The calculated distance to the lens star is slightly smaller and has a smaller uncertainty range than the distance to NGC 6544 that Gaia reports, implying that perhaps Gaia over-estimated this value.

Figure 5.3: Proper Motion of NGC 6544 and OGLE-2018-BLG-0705

Proper motions of stars in the field of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705. Bulge and disk stars are generally the stars above the dashed blue line, and NGC 6544 stars are generally those under the dashed blue line. The source star, shown in yellow, clearly resides in the bulge, whereas the solutions for the lens star, shown in green, orange (invisible on the plot because it entirely overlaps with the purple star), purple, and red are either calculated to reside in NGC 6544 (purple, orange) or just beyond the edge of the bulge population (red, green). The calculated value for the lens's proper motion when π_{EN} is negative is within 3-sigma (range shown in shaded purple) of the average proper motion for the star cluster (blue star), and is itself clearly consistent with other NGC 6544 star proper motions. On the other hand, the calculated proper motion for the lens star in Runs #1 and #4 is not consistent with the population of bulge stars in this observing field. This provides strong evidence that the lens of OGLE-2018-BLG-0705 resides in NGC 6544.

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